

HISTORY, OVERVIEW AND THE USE OF THE GRAMMAR TRANSLATION METHOD

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ABSTRACT

The Grammar Translation Method (GTM) has a long history, but has recently fallen out of favour as an effective method of second language acquisition. This article examines the origins and history of the GTM, its main features and contemporary criticism of the method. Particular attention is paid to the history and application of the grammatical translation method, as well as how it sometimes affects pedagogy.

Keywords: Grammar Translation Method, history, criticism, goal, principles

Language learning is almost as old as human history itself, and communication is an essential tool for the prosperity of all human societies. Some argue that the fact that over 50% of the world's population is multilingual today means that teaching and learning languages is still important today. Throughout history, different approaches and methodologies have emerged in the transmission of language learning. Some approaches have been around for a short time and have since fallen into disuse, while others have stood the test of time and can still be found in second language (L2) classrooms around the world.

This article looks at one such approach to language acquisition, the Grammar Translation Method (GTM), which has a very long history and is still used in L2 classrooms. Although some modern researchers and academics consider the GTM to be very old and obsolete, it is still the dominant doctrine in language teaching. Question: why? We examine the effectiveness of different levels of GTM and finally conclude which approaches to L2 English learning are most appropriate for students in today's educational environment.

What was later codified and compiled into a grammar translation method dates back to the early 16th century (McLelland, 2018). At that time, Latin was the lingua franca in most of Europe, primarily serving as the language used by the educated elite, as well as the language of philosophy, education, religion, culture and business (Celce-Murica, 2014). The "classical method", originally derived from the teaching of Latin, remained relatively unchanged until the 19th century, when Latin began to be replaced by other "modern" foreign languages in schools. In this technique, special attention was paid to the study of grammar rules through translation exercises. Since the ability

to communicate effectively in a language was considered only a secondary goal, conversational practice was minimal.

The Grammar Translation method is not new. It has had different names, it has been used by language teachers for many years it was called the Classical Method because it was the first method in teaching the classical languages like Latin and Greek. Earlier in this century, it was used for the purpose of helping students to read and appreciate foreign language literature.

In the late 19th century, leading German linguists began to systematize the basic elements of what was to become the method of language translation. Indeed, when GTM was first introduced in the United States, it was synonymous with German science and was known as the "Prussian method".

However, GTM was criticized early on by critics who advocated a "hands-on" approach to language learning. These critics advocated the use of communicative methods in the classroom, and by the 1930s most American classrooms had switched to the "reading" method, using specially designed textbooks for L2 students instead of translations writings of unrelated texts. During World War II, the US military developed a "phonological" approach to language teaching, and by the 1960s, this method had largely replaced GTM in the United States. However, in some parts of the world, translation has been the preferred approach and foreign language teachers can still be found in classrooms around the world.

The main features of the grammatical method of translation can be summarized as follows:

1. Students learn to translate directly from the target language into their native language.
2. Students learn grammatical rules deductively.
3. Lists of target words are presented with their native language equivalents.
4. In the process of teaching and learning, the mother tongue is mainly used, not the language of the student.
5. In the translation, great attention is paid to the correctness of the student, correction by the teacher, just giving the right answer.

Today, GTM is considered as obsolete by many modern language educators and out of place in the modern L2 classroom. Richards and Rogers, in their book *Approaches and Methods for Teaching Foreign Languages*, state: "It is true that the grammar and translation method is still widely used, but it has no supporters. This theory exists as a non-existent method."

Because spoken target language is rarely used in the GTM classroom, critics argue that this method fails to engage students in effective communication in the target language. However, this method is still widely used today because this approach has a

number of advantages: the teacher does not need to have special qualifications to be able to teach the target language.

Misunderstandings and communication difficulties between students and the teacher are minimized because the teacher can explain clearly in the students' native language. This will reduce the "loss of time" in the lesson. Students' understanding is easy to check because the teacher can ask questions in their native language.

Because the teacher is less involved, issues such as large classes and students with varying skill levels pose fewer problems with GTM.

Some recent research claims that the "communicative language learning" model dominates contemporary L2 learning. Some even argue that elements of grammar translation will inevitably come back into vogue and there will be more integration between CLT and GTM in the future, leading to a more complete learning of the language (Conti, 2015).

During World War II, it became apparent that neither the grammar translation method nor the reading methods provided students with enough language skills to communicate with allies or understand enemy messages. Therefore, the US government turned to methods based on the linguistic and psychological theories of the time, which were later adapted for use in public schools as an audio-lingual method. By the 1960s, the audio-lingual method had replaced the grammar and translation method of teaching foreign languages in most American classrooms. Grammar translation methods, however, continue to be used around the world to teach classical and sometimes modern languages, especially less studied languages.

GTM advocates and practitioners do not appear to have a developed theoretical basis for this method (Richards & Rodgers, 2001). However, this method is clearly based on the assumption that language is made up of structures and vocabulary, and is studied by examining these elements and using them to translate sentences and longer texts.

The goals of the method are to develop the ability to read literature in the language being studied, as well as to develop "excellent mental discipline, courage and a broad human understanding of life." "Mental discipline" is believed to be enhanced by analyzing complex grammatical structures. A secondary objective is to improve students' understanding of the mother tongue through the practice of grammar analysis.

CONCLUSION

Although the grammatical translation method largely dispenses with any reference to common usage, it is still used today in the teaching of foreign languages, especially in third world countries. Much of its popularity stems from its relatively simple training requirements. Anyone with good reading and writing skills can teach a language using the Grammar Translation Method, knowledge of the target language is

not required. Therefore, it is clear that this method will always have its place in the field of teaching foreign languages to some extent and its use will not disappear.

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